

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF GASTRORETENTIVE FLOATING MATRIX SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLETS OF LAFUTIDINE

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ABSTRACT

This study presents with formulation and the evaluation of gastroretentive floating matrix of the sustained release tablets of the lafutidine, which is an anti-ulcerative agent of the narrow absorption window in the upper GI tract. This aims at the bioavailability and therapeutic efficacy using hydrophobic polymers of floating drug delivery system (FDDS) such as HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M and the tamarind seed polysaccharide (TSP), including the effervescent of (sodium bicarbonate and citric acid) for ensuring the buoyancy. The tablets has been prepared by the direct compression and it is evaluated for the pre-compression and post compression including

KEYWORDS - Lafutidine, gastroretentive, hydrophobic polymers, floating drug delivery system.

1.INTRODUCTION

Oral route of drug delivery is preferred route for the ease administration. The bioavailability of drug has been influenced by the various factors for the oral pharmaceutical dosage forms(1). The most important factor will be the gastric residence time (GRT) of those dosage forms. Indeed, the gastric retention time it has received an impactful interest in the past decades of the most conventional oral route of delivery which shows limitations to the fast gastric emptying time(2).A gastro retentive dosage form (GRDF) can overcome this problem and is particularly Useful for drugs that are primarily absorbed in the duodenum and super jejunum segments.

The stomach is divided into three anatomic regions: fundus, body and antrum (pylorus). The pylorus has been separated between the stomach

weight variation, floating time, friability, hardness, swelling index, drug content and the release of invitro drug. From the developed 13 formulations (F1-F13), formulation F4 has been identified as the optimized batch for its favourable buoyancy, swelling index, and sustained drug release upto 12hrs with 97.86% release. FTIR and DSC studies has confirmed that the absence of drug-polymer interactions and studies of stability indicated that no significant change over the 60 days under the accelerated conditions. The kinetics of drug release followed zero-order release and the non-Fickian diffusion, which has suggested a combination of the diffusion and the erosion of mechanisms. This study concludes that the lafutidine matrix provide an approach for the prolonged gastric retention and the control drug delivery system, which improves patient compliance and the therapeutic outcomes.

and the duodenum. The part made of fundus and body acts as a reservoir for undigested material, whereas the antrum is the main site for mixing motions act as a pump for gastric emptying by propelling actions(2,3). The gastric emptying will occur at the fasting states also in the state of fed. The

motility of pattern is distinct between the two states. During the fasting state an interdigestive series of electrical states. During the fasting state an interdigestive series of electrical events take place, which cycle both through stomach and intestine every 2-3hrs.

Phase I (Basal phase) lasts from 40 to 60 min with rare contractions.Phase II (preburst phase) lasts from 40 to 60 min with intermittent action potential

and contractions. When the phase gets progressed its intensity and the frequency will be increased gradually. Phase III (Burst phase) lasts for 4-6 min. It also

This results in an increased gastric retention time and a better control of the fluctuations in plasma

S.No	Name of material	Manufacturer / supplier	Use in formulation
1	Lafutidine	Pure Chem Pvt Ltd.	Active ingredient
2	HPMC K15	Fourrts India Laboratories Pvt Ltd.	Hydrophilic polymer
3	HPMC K4	Fourrts India Laboratories Pvt Ltd.	Hydrophilic polymer
4	Tamarind seed polysaccharide	Preparing in laboratory	Sustained Release Matrix type Agent and Floating Agent

includes an intense and the contractions regular for short time of period. This is the wave which sweeps out the undigested material from the stomach, down into the small intestine, which is also known as house keeper wave. Phase IV lasts for 0-5min are a transition period of decreasing activity until the next cycle begins(4).

The present work was to develop a new and innovative gastro retentive formulation based on intrinsic low- density(floating) systems using a standard manufacturing process (the wet granulation and the moulding of the tablets have been chosen), allowing a final porous structure with improved cohesion and which releases drugs in the stomach and upper gastrointestinal tract (GI).

Floating drug delivery system (FDDS) or dynamically controlled hydro systems which are low-density that have appropriate buoyancy to float on the gastric contents and it can be remain as buoyant inside the stomach which will not be affected by gastric emptying rate for extended period of time(3). While the systems is floating on the gastric contents, the drug is released slowly at the desired rate from the system. After release of drug, the residual systems is emptied from the stomach.

drug concentration. However, besides a minimal gastric content needed to allow the proper achievement of the buoyancy retention principle, a minimal level of floating force(F) is also required to keep the dosage from reliably buoyant on the surface of the meal. To measure the floating force kinetics, a novel apparatus operates by measuring continuously the force equivalent to F (as a function of time) that is required to Maintain the submerged object, the object floats better if F is on the higher positive side(5). This system helps in

2.MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 MATERIAL

the optimizing the FDDS in order to stability and also the durability of the floating forces respected to the prevention of the drawbacks in the variations of unforceable intragastric capability.

Gastro retentive drug delivery system (GRDDS) is a site-specific drug delivery system. It delivers the drug either in stomach or in intestine. The drug delivery is obtained by retention of dosage form in stomach and the drug is released in the controlled manner to the specific site either in stomach, duodenum or in the intestine. Gastro retentive drug delivery is an approach to prolong gastric residence time, thereby targeting site-specific drug release in

the upper part of gastrointestinal tract (GIT) for local or systemic effects(2,4). The gastro retentive dosages can be left remain in the region of gastric for the prolonged period and hence it is significantly extends the gastric retention time of the drugs.

Over the last few decades, several gastro retentive drug delivery approaches being designed and developed, including: High density (sinking) systems that is retained in the bottom of the stomach, Low density (floating) systems that causes buoyancy in gastric fluid, muco adhesive systems that causes bio adhesion to stomach mucosa, un foldable, extendible, or swellable systems which limits emptying of the dosage forms through the pyloric sphincter of stomach, super porous hydro gel systems, magnetic systems etc(4,5).

5	Sodium bicarbonate	Fourrts India Laboratories Pvt Ltd	Effervescent Agent
6	Citric Acid	Fourrts India Laboratories Pvt Ltd.	Effervescent Agent
7	Micro crystalline cellulose	Paris Dakner Pvt Ltd.	Binding agent
8	Talc	Paris Dakner Pvt Ltd.	Glidant
9	Magnesium Stearate	Paris Dakner Pvt Ltd.	Lubricant

2.2EQUIPMENTS

S.No	EQUIPMENT'S / INSTRUMENTS	MANUFACTURER / SUPPLIER
1	Electronic weighing balance	A & D company HR 200, Japan.
2	Hot air oven	RANDS Instruments Company, Chennai.
3	Single Punch tablet compression machine	Cadmach Machinery Co.Pvt., Ahmadabad
4	Vernier caliper	Linker, Mumbai.
5	Monsanto hardness tester	Praveen Enterprises, Bangalore.
6	Friability Test Apparatus	Indian Equipment Corporation.
7	pH meter	MC Dalal, Chennai
8	Disintegration apparatus	Electrolab, India
9	Digital Tablet Dissolution Test Apparatus	Disso 2000 Lab India, Mumbai.
10	UV-visible spectrophotometer	UV-1700 Pharmaspec Shimadzu, Japan
11	Fourier transform infra-red spectrophotometer	Shimadzu RXI Japan.

2.3 METHODOLOGY

2.3.1 DRUG CONTENT

Weight of the powder material equivalent to 10 mg of Lafutidine is taken and transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask. Then 30 ml of Acid buffer PH 1.2 is added slowly, mixed properly and the volume is made up to 100 ml with Acid buffer PH 1.2. The above solution is filtered and 10 ml of filtrate is taken into 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to final volume with Acid buffer PH 1.2 and the drug content is estimated by measuring the absorbance at λ max 283 nm using a UV- spectrophotometer.

2.3.2 HARDNESS TEST

The tablet should withstand the strength or the hardness and also resistance to the friability for to withstand the mechanical shock while handling in the manufacture, shipping and the packing(6). To measure the hardness of the tablet using the Mosanto hardness tester. In each of the batch 3 tablets are used to test the hardness and the results can be expressed in the kg/cm²(7).

2.3.3 FRIABILITY TEST

It is done in Roche friabilator apparatus where the tablets are subjected to the combined effect of abrasion and shock by utilizing a plastic chamber that revolves at 25 rpm for dropping the tablets at a distance of six inches with each revolution. Pre weighed samples of 20 tablets are placed in the friabilator, which is then operated for 100 revolutions(6). The tablets has been dusted and the it is reweighed. The tablets that has been compressed can loss lesser than 0.5 - 1.0% of the weight can be acceptable.

2.3.4 DRUG CONTENT UNIFORMITY

Ten tablets have been weighed and placed in a mortar and then crushed for making into a powder form. A quantity of powder weighing equivalent to 10mg of drug is taken in a 100ml volumetric flask and Acid buffer PH 1.2 is added(10). The solution is filtered using membrane filter (0.45 μ m) and 10 ml of filtrate is taken into 100 ml volumetric flask and made up to final volume with Acid buffer PH 1.2(7). Then its absorbance is measured at 283nm using

UV Visible spectrometer. The amount of the drug present in the each tablet can be calculated using the standardised graph(12).

2.3.5 EVALUATION OF SELECTED BEST FORMULATION:

2.3.5.1 INFRARED SPECTROSCOPIC STUDIES:

The interaction between the drug and excipient / polymer are studied by FT-IR as per the procedure.

2.3.5.2 DIFFERENTIAL SCANNING CALORIMETRIC STUDIES (DSC):

Differential scanning calorimetry is carried out to find out any incompatibility between the drug and excipients used.

2.3.6 COMPARISON WITH CONVENTIONAL TABLET FORMULATION:

The release of the best formulation is compared with the marketed formulation

2.3.6.1 STABILITY STUDIES Stability studies were carried out by using selected formulation i.e F4(9). The formulation is kept in accelerated stability condition at 40^oC temperature $75 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity for a period of 2 months as per International Conference on Harmonization guidelines (Mathews, 1999; International Conference on Harmonization Steering Committee,1999).The samples were withdrawn at every 15 days intervals and evaluation was carried out for appearance, thickness, hardness, buoyancy lag time, drug content and *In-vitro* release studies (60 days).

2.3.6.2 WEIGHT VARIATION TEST

Randomly 20 tablets have been selected and it is weighed individually in an electronic balance and then the average weight has been calculated(11). The weight of the uniformity has been determined by the IP accordance(8). As per IP not more than two of individual weights should deviate from average weight by more than 5% and none deviate more than twice that percentage. The following

percentage deviation in weight variation is shown in the table no 1.

TABLE NO : 1 WEIGHT VARIATION TEST

Parameter	Specifications
Dissolution Medium	Buffer 0.1N hydrochloric Acid
Temperature	37.0 ± 0.5 °C
Initial Volume	900ml
Rotation Speed	75rpm
Drawn Volume	5ml
Running Time	12 hrs. in 0.1N hydrochloric Acid

TABLE NO : 2 In vitro drug release studies

temperature of the medium is set at 37°C ± 0.5°C(14). One tablet of different batch is placed in each dissolution vessel and the rotational

2.3.6.3 IN VITRO DRUG RELEASE STUDIES:

Dissolution characteristics of the formulated floating tablets of Lafutidine are carried out using USP Type II (paddle) dissolution test apparatus for 12hrs(13).

2.3.7 METHOD:

900 ml of acid buffer pH 1.2 was filled in dissolution vessel and

speed of paddle was set at 75rpm as shown in the table no 2. 5ml of sample is withdrawn at pre-determined time interval of every one hour for up to 12 hours and same volume of fresh medium is replaced immediately(15). The withdrawn sample is diluted to 10ml in volumetric flask and filtered through 0.45µ membrane filter. The resultant samples are analyzed for drug content at 283nm using

UV-Visible spectrophotometer.

be 0.9995 which indicate Lirafutidine obeys Beer's law within concentration range of 5 - 25µg/ml.

3.2 DRUG-POLYMER COMPATIBILITY STUDIES

3.2.1 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopic studies (FT-IR)

Infrared spectroscopic analysis was performed to check out the compatibility between the drug (Lirafutidine) and the hydrophilic polymers (HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M,) and Tamar seed polysaccharides used in the formulation of floating matrix tablets. IR spectrum of the drug and the physical mixtures of drug with polymers of optimized formulation were studied. Mixtures of drug and polymers showed that there was no shifting of functional peaks. All the major peaks present in the spectrum of pure drug were clearly observed in the spectrum of physical mixtures with negligible changes. The results obtained have clearly shown that there are no interactions between the polymers and drugs.

TABLE NO : 3 THE FT-IR SPECTRA OF PURE DRUG LIRAFUTIDINE

Spectroscopy (UV)

The absorption maximum (λ_{max}) of Lirafutidine was estimated by scanning the drug solution (10µg/ml) between 200-400nm regions on UV spectrophotometer. The obtained spectrum showed that the absorption maximum (λ_{max}) was 283nm in Acid buffer PH 1.2.

3.1.3 Preparation of standard calibration curve for Lirafutidine

The standard calibration curve for Lirafutidine was prepared by using acid buffer PH 1.2. The absorbance was measured at λ_{max} of 283nm. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9995. The results clearly showed that there was no interaction between the drug and polymers.

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 STANDARD CALIBRATION CURVE FOR LIRAFUTIDINE:

3.1.1 Preparation of dissolution medium

The preparation of dissolution medium was prepared by using Acid buffer PH 1.2 (Indian pharmacopoeia 1996, volume: 2, page no: A-144)

3.1.2 Estimation of absorption maximum (λ_{max}) for Lirafutidine by Ultraviolet

All the major peaks present in the spectrum of pure drug were clearly observed in the spectrum of physical mixtures with negligible changes. The obtained results clearly showed that there

**3.3 FORMULATION OF
SUSTAINED RELEASE
FLOATING MATRIX TABLET
EFFERVESCENT TECHNIQUE
(F4)**

The Lafutidine floating tablets were prepared by effervescent technique used the hydrophilic polymers (HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M, and Tamarind seed polysaccharides). Sodium bicarbonate & citric acid used as gas generating agent. The polymers were chosen as they are well established in the similar studies and have great swelling and sustained release properties respectively. From the trial studies, the formula was optimized depending on the floating behavior of the tablets.

RELEASE MATRIX TABLET

Quantity (mg) for I tablet (Average weight -200mg)

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13
Lafutidine	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Tamarind seed poly saccharides	2	4	6	8	10	12	2	4	6	8	10	12	-
HPMCK4	140	130	120	110	100	90	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
HPMCK15	-	-	-	-	-	-	140	130	120	110	100	90	-
Sodium bicarbonate	20	25	30	35	40	45	20	25	30	35	40	45	-
Citric acid	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	-
Talc	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Magnesium stearate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Microcrystalline Cellulose	16	19	22	25	28	31	16	19	22	25	28	31	184

Total weight	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
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FORMULATION OF EFFERVESCENT FLOATING SUSTAINED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS

Average Weight 200mg / Tablet

S.no	Ingredients	Quantity (mg) for 1 tablet 200 mg
1	Lafutidine	10
2	Tamarind seed polysaccharides	8
3	HPMC k4	110
4	Sodium bicarbonate	35
5	Citric acid	6
6	Talc	2
7	Magnesium stearate	4
8	Micro crystalline cellulose	25
Total weight		200

EVALUATION OF LAFUTIDINE FLOATING TABLETS KEPT IN STABILITY AT 40°C / 75% RELATIVE HUMIDITY EVALUATION OF STABILITY STUDIES BEST FORMULATION (F4)

Formulation Parameters	Initial	15 days	30days	45days	60days
Average weight (mg)	198.46	198.38	198.31	198.41	198.45
Thickness (mg)	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39	3.39

Hardness (kg/cm ²)	7.2	7.13	7.16	7.2	7.16
Floating lag Time(sec)	14sec	14sec	14sec	14 sec	15sec
Swelling Index (8 Hours) (%)	65.57	65.34	65.06	64.97	64.56
Drug content in %	98.99%±0.34	98.79%±0.6	98.59%±0.346	98.39%±0.34	98.39%±0.34
% drug release at 12hrs	97.86±0.6373	-----	-----	----	96.09 ±0.271

Stability studies were carried out by using selected formulation i.e. F4. The formulation is kept in accelerated stability condition at 40^oC temperature 75 ± 5% relative humidity for a period of 2 months as per International Conference on Harmonization guidelines (Mathews, 1999; International Conference on Harmonization Steering Committee,1999).The samples were withdrawn at every 15 days intervals and evaluation was carried out for appearance, thickness, hardness, buoyancy lag time, drug content and *In-vitro* release studies (60days)

FIG.DETERMINATION OF λ_{max} OF LAFUTIDINE IN ACID BUFFER pH 1.2

FIG. CALIBRATION OF LAFUTIDINE USING ACID BUFFER pH 1.2

FIG.19 HAUSNER'S RATIO OF FORMULATIONS(F1.F13)

FIG.20 DRUG CONTENT OF ALL FOMULATIONS (F1-F13)

FIG.21 SWELLING INDEX OF ALL FORMULTIONS (F1-F12)

**FIG.22AIN-VITRO BUOYANCY STUDIES OF FLOATING TABLET
OF LAFUTIDINE BEST FORMULATION F4**

(A) 0 seconds

(B) 3rd second

FIG.22AIN-VITRO BUOYANCY STUDIES OF FLOATING TABLET

(C) 6th second

(D) 9th second

FIG. 22B *IN-VITRO* BUOYANCY STUDIES OF FLOATING TABLET OF LAFUTIDINE BEST FORMULATION F4

(E) 12th second

(F) 14th second

FIG.23 *IN -VITRO* SWELLING INDEX STUDIES OF FLOATING TABLET OF LAFUTIDINE BEST FORMULATION F4

FIG.24A *IN-VITRO* DRUG RELEASE PROFILE OF LAFUTIDINE WITH TSP AND HPMCK4 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

FIG.24B *IN-VITRO* DRUG RELEASE PROFILE OF LAFUTIDINE WITH TSP AND HPMCK4 AT DIFFERENT

FIG.24C IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE PROFILE OF LAFUTIDINE WITH TSP AND HPMCK15 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

FIG.24D IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE PROFILE OF LAFUTIDINE WITH TSP AND HPMCK15 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

HPMCK15 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

FIG.24E *IN-VITRO* DRUG RELEASE PROFILE OF LAFUTIDINE CONVENTIONAL TABLET

FIG.25A COMPARISON OF *IN-VITRO* FIRST ORDER RELEASE KINETICS OF FORMULATION CONTAINING TSP AND HPMCK4 AT

DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

FIG.25B COMPARISON OF *IN-VITRO* FIRST ORDER RELEASE KINETICS OF FORMULATION CONTAINING TSP AND HPMCK4 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

FIG.25C COMPARISON OF *IN-VITRO* FIRST ORDER RELEASE KINETICS OF FORMULATION CONTAINING TSP AND HPMCK15 AT

DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

FIG.25D COMPARISON OF *IN-VITRO* FIRST ORDER RELEASE KINETICS OF FORMULATION CONTAINING TSP AND HPMCK15 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

FIG.26A COMPARISON OF *IN-VITRO* ZERO ORDER KINETICS OF

FORMULATION CONTAINING NATURAL POLYMER AND HPMCK4 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

FIG. 31 EVALUATION OF LAFUTIDINE FLOATING SUSTAINED RELEASE MATRIX KEPT IN STABILITY AT 40°C/75% RELATIVE HUMIDITY

FORMULATION CONTAINING TSP AND HPMCK4 AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

FIG.26C COMPARISON OF *IN-VITRO* ZERO ORDER KINETICS OF FORMULATION CONTAINING TSP AND HPMCK15 AT

DIFFERENT CONCENTRATION

The Lafutidine obeys the Beer's law within the concentration of 5 to 20 μ g/ml.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Floating Drug Delivery System are retained in the stomach for a longer time and assist in improving the oral sustained release delivery of drugs that have an absorption window in the particular region of the GI tract as well as for sustained the release of the drug having site-specific absorption limitation.

Lafutidine is a highly effective anti-ulcer drug was used as a model drug to develop a sustained release formulation.

Lafutidine freely soluble in glacial acetic acid. Hence an attempt was made to develop gastro retentive delivery system of Lafutidine are designed to prolong the gastric residence time, increase the drug bioavailability, diminish the side effects of irritating drugs and also to reduce frequency of administration, thereby improving patient compliance and therapeutic efficacy.

The λ max of Lafutidine was found to be 283nm in 0.1N hydrochloric acid.

FTIR & DSC studies showed that there was no interaction between drug and polymers.

The floating matrix tablets were prepared by direct compression method using different concentrations of gel forming hydrophilic polymers by effervescent technique.

The formulated tablets were analysed for pre compression and post compression parameter, swelling index, *invitro* drug release studies, *invitro* kinetics & *in-vivo* x-ray studies.

The pre compression parameters of all the formulations were within the required limit was indicated good flow property, suitable for formulation of the tablets.

The post compression parameters such as thickness, hardness, friability, uniformity of content and swelling index of all formulations were within the acceptable limits.

The floating lag time & total floating time were found to be satisfied.

F4 formulation was selected as best formulation based on in-vitro release studies, swelling studies & in-vitro buoyancy studies. The extent of drug release was found to be 97.86 in 12hrs.

The drug release model of this formulation (F4) complies with zero order kinetics Followed by Non-fickian diffusion mechanism.

FTIR & DSC studies of selected best formulation shows that no interaction between the drug and polymers.

Selected formulation showed sustained release profile than the conventional tablet.

The floating matrix tablets of Lafutidine by effervescent technique also developed for comparison of conventional tablet

CONCLUSION

The results conclusively demonstrated that floating tablets of Lafutidine was effectively prepared by direct compression method with desired properties and exhibited better in-vitro drug

release profiles. The formulation F4 containing HPMC K4 exhibit least floating lag time and maximum rate of drug release. So, this formulation was considered to be the optimized formulation. The developed floating tablets of Lafutidine may be used for prolonged drug release, there by improving the bioavailability and patient compliance over other dosage forms.

Tamarind seed polysaccharides (TSP) was found to be a promising low density material in the formulation of floating matrix tablets of Lafutidine in combination with gel forming hydrophilic polymers like HPMC K4M, HPMC K15M. Use of Natural polymers with Tamarind seed polysaccharides enhanced the floating duration and maintained the dimensional stability, which is an important requirement and it is a potential polysaccharide having high drug holding capacity which can sustained the release of drugs. The drug release was sustained properly up to 12 hrs. Based on this work it was found that effervescent type of floating drug delivery systems holds a lot of potential and comparable with Conventional tablet.

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